

HOKKAIDO UNIVERSITY
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COURSE IN CRYOSPHERE SCIENCE

Influence of basal input data on spin-up simulations of the
Antarctic ice sheet
(南極氷床のスピンアップシミュレーションにおける底面境界条件の影響)

Master's Thesis

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Abstract

Initial conditions have a non-negligible effect on the future evolution of the Antarctic ice sheet. Therefore, to model the future of the ice sheet, an accurate state of the present-day ice sheet is needed. The ice sheet model used here (SICOPOLIS, SIMulation COde for POLythermal Ice Sheets) needs all input datasets to coincide with the grid resolution. We have integrated two up-to-date basal datasets: the geothermal heat flux (GHF) “Aq1” (Stål et al., 2021), and the bed topography, for which we combined the BedMachine3 dataset for the entire ice sheet (Morlighem et al., 2020) with more recent, local data in the vicinity of Dome Fuji (Tsutaki et al., 2022). As these datasets come with widely different resolutions, some grid interpolations were necessary and, in case of the bed topography, we had to create a smooth transition zone between the ice-sheet-wide data and the local data around Dome Fuji to avoid discontinuities.

However, some variables are largely unknown and have not been measured, such as the 3D temperature distribution in the ice sheet. Some variables also have a memory of the past, such as the previously mentioned temperature field, as well as the glacial isostatic adjustment, and thus are still affected by the presence of a larger and colder ice sheet during the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM). To capture those time dependencies and unknown variables, a paleoclimatic ‘spin-up’ simulation is necessary, for which the present-day data (surface and bed topographies, GHF, surface velocity) are used as inputs and constraints. Berends et al. (2023) developed a new spin-up framework, which we adapted and integrated into SICOPOLIS. This framework has four subsequent phases. The first phase, over 100 ka with a constant, present-day climate forcing, is used to iteratively find the basal sliding coefficients for 18 regions of the ice sheet. The ice sheet is then left to evolve freely and gain mass in the second phase from the Eemian interglacial 125 ka ago until the LGM 20 ka ago. The third phase runs from the LGM until the early Holocene 9 ka ago, nudging

the topography (by systematically adjusting the surface mass balance) towards the geometry of the present-day ice sheet. The last phase, from 9 ka ago until today, continues the nudging to get an accurate present-day geometry, and another round of iterative tuning of the sliding coefficients is done.

In agreement with pertinent reconstructions, we found that the simulated LGM ice sheet is significantly larger than today's in terms of volume and area of grounded ice. The simulated present-day ice sheet retains this memory from the LGM through englacial temperature and residual isostatic uplift, and it has an accurate present-day geometry and a surface velocity field that matches observations reasonably well. Therefore, this present-day ice sheet is well suited as an initial state for simulations of its future evolution under warming climates.

1 Introduction

Global warming, driven by human activities, and its accelerated effects in polar regions, poses significant challenges as melting ice sheets contribute to rising sea levels and disrupt delicate ecosystems, emphasizing the urgent need to study climate change and its impact on ice sheets. Simulations of the Antarctic ice sheet (AIS) play a crucial role in understanding its behavior, predicting future changes, and informing strategies for mitigating the consequences of global warming.

As shown in the `initMIP` experiment (Seroussi et al., 2019), initial conditions have a non-negligible effect on the output of future climate simulations of the Antarctic ice sheet. In order to model the future of the ice sheet, an integrated version of the present day ice sheet is necessary (geometry, temperature fields, etc.). Some variables are measured, such as the bed elevation and ice thickness (Morlighem et al., 2020). However, some variables are unknown and have not been measured, such as the temperature field or basal sliding parameters.

Moreover, the temperature and the Glacial Isostatic Adjustment (GIA) have time dependency, and thus are still affected by the presence of a larger ice sheet during the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM). In order to capture those time dependencies and unknown variables, a preliminary simulation is necessary, called ‘spin-up’, in which all the well-known data is used as an input. This initialization can take many forms, the most common ones being:

1. steady state equilibrium: The ice sheet is left to evolve in a present-day climate, in equilibrium until the temperature fields develop.
2. Data assimilation: The ice sheet is left to relax for a short simulation.
3. Paleoclimatic spin-up: The model goes through past climates (including LGM), and simulated until present day.

However, these spin-up methods bear some limitations, in the case of the methods

1 and 2, temperature or GIA memory are missing. For the 3rd method, it is challenging to end up with an accurate present-day ice sheet.

In order to get a more accurate present-day ice sheet, Berends and Bernales (Berends et al., 2023) developed a new spin-up framework, which we will adapt and integrate into SICOPOLIS (SIMulation CODE for POLythermal Ice Sheets). Using this new spin-up procedure, and the latest basal data available (Geothermal heat flux and ice thickness), to get an accurate present-day Antarctic ice sheet, ready for future climate simulations, and evaluate the gains from the memory's presence.

2 Ice sheet model SICOPOLIS

The SICOPOLIS model, initially designed for the Greenland ice sheet, has been continuously developed since its creation in 1995 and 1997 (Greve, 1995, 1997). It has been widely applied to various glaciation-related issues, including the past, present, and future conditions of the ice sheets of Greenland, Antarctica, the Northern Hemisphere, and even the polar ice caps of Mars (Stenzel et al., 2007).

For this thesis, we use SICOPOLIS (SICOPOLIS Authors, 2023) specifically for modeling the Antarctic ice sheet. The model encompasses the entire Antarctic region, including the surrounding oceans. To facilitate the computations, we adopt the EPSG:3031 grid, which employs a polar stereographic projection with the WGS 84 reference ellipsoid, a standard parallel of 71°S, and a central meridian of 0°E. The stereographic plane is defined by Cartesian coordinates (x, y) . The grid is discretized into a regular grid with a resolution of either 8, 16, or 32 km for Δx and Δy . In the vertical dimension, we employ terrain-following coordinates (sigma transformation) with 81 layers in the ice domain and 41 layers in the thermal lithosphere layer below. The time steps used here will range from 0.25 a for the coarser resolutions to 0.1 a at 16 km of resolution.

Ice dynamics are modeled as follows:

- Grounded ice: hybrid shallow-ice-shelfy-stream (Bernales et al., 2017)
- Floating ice: Shallow shelf approximation (SSA) (e.g. Greve and Blatter (2009))

The ice surface is assumed to be traction-free, and the grounded ice basal sliding is described by a Weertman-Budd-type sliding law (Hindmarsh and Le Meur, 2001), accounting for sub-melt sliding, as well as the subglacial water thickness (Kleiner and Humbert, 2014; Calov et al., 2018). The sliding law will be explored in further detail in Section 4.2.

The glacial isostatic adjustment is computed using the elastic lithosphere, relaxing asthenosphere (ELRA) model, with parameters from Sato and Greve (2012). The

surface and bed elevation, as well as the geothermal heat fluxes will be described in Section 3.

The climate of the past is decomposed into a present-day spatial distribution $T_{present}$ (Fortuin and Oerlemans, 1990) and a time-dependent temperature anomaly $\Delta T(t)$ (Petit et al., 1999).

The surface mass balance is derived through a combination of positive degree day (PDD) for surface melting (where days with positive temperature are accounted for melting), and the parametrization by Huybrechts et al. (2007) (computed by using a combination of present-day precipitation and a temperature-dependent factor). Calving of floating ice is done through a strict removal of the ice as soon as its thickness goes under 50 m (Sato and Greve, 2012).

Simulations are also constrained by a temporal series of surface temperature anomalies (Petit et al., 1999) and a temporal series of sea level (Imbrie et al., 1984).

3 Basal input data

3.1 Bed and surface elevations

Since SICOPOLIS previously utilized Bedmap2 (Fretwell et al., 2013), which is now 10 years old, the initial task involved integrating the newly released BedMachine3 dataset (Morlighem et al., 2020) into SICOPOLIS. This integration process involved adapting a script developed by Prof. Ralf Greve specifically for Greenland. Additionally, the original BedMachine3 data had a resolution of 500 m, necessitating downsampling and adjustment to align with the SICOPOLIS grid. This adjustment was achieved through a weighted average of the BedMachine3 grid cells overlapping with each SICOPOLIS grid cell, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Illustration of the downsampling process. Red square is a SICOPOLIS grid cell, black-bordered squares are BedMachine grid cells. The SICOPOLIS grid point value is a weighted average of the values in each point, the weights being the fractional area of each BedMachine cell inside the SICOPOLIS cell.

Furthermore, a more recent dataset by Tsutaki et al. (2022) from the JARE expeditions, offering accurate bed elevation and ice thickness data around the Dome Fuji area (Figure 2), was also integrated into the model. This was accomplished by patchworking the new data into BedMachine3 before incorporating it into SICOPOLIS.

To ensure a smooth transition between the Dome Fuji dataset and BedMachine3, the newer data was slightly smoothed at the interface where the two datasets overlapped, using an average of the bed elevation of the cells around the cells at the edges where the JARE dataset region meets BedMachine3. Afterward, this final version of BedMachine (referred to as BedMachine-JARE for the remainder of this thesis) was downsampled using the aforementioned method to match all the supported resolutions in SICOPOLIS. In this paper, the resolutions used are 8 km, 16 km, and 32 km.

It might be tempting to assume that the gains from transitioning from Bedmap2 to BedMachine3 diminish as the resolution decreases. However, as depicted in Figure 3, even with increasingly large averaging during downsampling to lower resolutions, substantial differences between Bedmap2 and BedMachine3 persist. The root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) is approximately 100 m, with certain areas exhibiting ice thickness differences exceeding 2000 m.

Figure 2: Left: The position of Dome Fuji on an Antarctic ice thickness map. Right: Ice thickness difference between BedMachine3 and BedMachine3-JARE patchworked.

Figure 3: Ice thickness difference between BedMachine3 and Bedmap2 over the Antarctic continent. Left: 8 km resolution. Right: 32 km resolution.

3.2 Geothermal heat flux

Three distinct geothermal heat fluxes (GHF) will be employed in this study (see Figure 4). The first two (Purucker, 2012; Fox Maule et al., 2005; Martos et al., 2017) were indirectly derived by matching heat conduction models with observed magnetic satellite data. The third and most recent GHF map (Stål et al., 2021) was obtained using a similarity approach with data from other continents, incorporating previous geothermal heat flux datasets of Antarctica as references.

To incorporate the latest GHF map (Aq1, Stål et al. (2021)) into SICOPOLIS, some integration was required. However, the original dataset had a resolution of 20 km, necessitating interpolation (linear interpolation in this case) to match SICOPOLIS' native resolutions before it could be utilized.

One last thing to note is that the oldest dataset (abbreviated Pu or Purucker, Purucker (2012)) has the lowest average GHF (54 mW m^{-2}). The second oldest (called Martos) has the highest average GHF (67 mW m^{-2}), and finally the newest data, Aq1, in between (62 mW m^{-2}). These differences, especially in the East Antarctic Ice Sheet (EAIS), will compound and allow for much more mass gain in the region. More on that in Section 4.

Figure 4: geothermal heat flux map. Top-left: The older dataset by Purucker (2012). Top-right: Dataset by Martos et al. (2017). Bottom: Newest dataset, by Stål et al. (2021).

4 Model experiments

4.1 General set-up

The initial configuration for our simulations is based on the set-up employed in the ISMIP6-Antarctica simulations, as outlined by Greve et al. (2020). However, we made adjustments to the flow enhancement factors by incorporating the reference values and parameters utilized in the studies conducted by Albrecht et al. (2020a,b)

4.2 Transient spin-up framework

The new spin-up framework developed by Berends and Bernales (Berends et al., 2023) is multiphase. There are 4 different phases spanning a total of 225 ka (see Figure 5), in the adapted version we produced for SICOPOLIS. The idea behind this new framework is to get at the end of the long spin-up period an Antarctic Ice Sheet (AIS) with accurate present-day topographic features (lithosphere, surface and ice thickness), with temperature and GIA signals from the last glacial maximum, when the AIS was bigger and thicker. Each phase is a different simulation, and each one of them (except the first one) takes as initial conditions the output of the previous phase. The four phases are as follows:

- Calibration phase: A short 100-years run for initial smoothing of the AIS, followed by a long, 100 ka steady-state run, using present-day climate. The end of this run is used for inverting unknown parameters (see Section 4.1.1), and is constrained by present-day geometry.
- Glacial phase: Another long 105 ka run (-125 ka to -20 ka), where the AIS is left to freely evolve, in order to get the last glacial maximum-sized ice sheet.
- Deglacial phase: A shorter transition (-20 ka to -9 ka) run, where the AIS is evolving using the present-day geometry as a target. The goal is to have it lose

mass, to the point where it is close to the present day ice sheet.

- Holocene phase: Last phase (-9 ka to present-day), with present-day geometry as a target, and used to fine-tune the parameters found during the calibration phase. The goal is to have an accurate, present-day ice sheet with thermal and GIA signals.

Figure 5: Antarctic ice volume in sea level equivalent over the entirety of the spin-up protocol, over time in ka.

One immediate drawback we can see from this spin-up framework is the sheer time needed for the spin up protocol to end. Most Antarctic simulations predict up to a few millennia past present at the highest resolutions (usually 5 to 20 km). In contrast, this spin-up needs to be run for more than 200 ka, making it virtually impossible to run at low resolutions because of the high computational costs and very long run times: at 32 km resolution, the glacial phase ends on the timescale of days, which would be weeks at higher resolutions. In order to alleviate the long run times, the calibration and glacial phases will be run at a resolution of 32 km. The output of the glacial phase will have its resolution doubled (using the `resolution_doubler` tool

from SICOPOLIS), and used as input for the deglacial phase. Finally, the Holocene phase will run at 16 km of resolution, using as input the output of the deglacial phase, doubling its resolution. Although most of the spin-up is run at a coarse resolution of 32 km resolution, the most time-costly simulations were the shorter ones at 16 km. Efforts were made to have either the entire Holocene phase or a later part of it done at 8 km of resolution, but the computation times were too long considering the time constraints of this thesis.

Finally, this framework is first tested using Aq1 as the GHF map, at 32 km resolution until the end, and once the parameters have been decided, applied to an ensemble of runs, with the resolutions described in the previous paragraph. These runs all use BedMachine3 plus the JARE Dome Fuji dataset for its topography, and the only difference is the GHF map, for which either Aq1, Martos or Pu will be used.

4.2.1 Calibration phase

The calibration phase starts with a short, 100 years equilibrium run in order to smoothen the ice sheet. The short smoothing run was done for resolutions of 8, 16 and 32 km. Then the output from the 32 km resolution smoothing run is used as an ice geometry target for the rest of the spin-up protocol.

First let's expand on what we mean by target. A technique called 'nudging' is used in order to constrain the ice sheet geometry, done through dynamic changes in the surface mass balance of the AIS (on top of the calculated surface mass balance) in order to match as closely as possible the simulated ice sheet to a prescribed geometry (in this case, the output from the short smoothing run). This is done through the following equations, where $h(x, y), b(x, y)$ are the surface and bed elevation, respectively, and τ_{relax} is the relaxation time:

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = -\frac{h - h_{target}}{\tau_{relax}}$$

$$\frac{\partial b}{\partial t} = -\frac{b - b_{target}}{\tau_{relax}}$$

The next step in the calibration phase is the inversion of unknown parameters. In SICOPOLIS, the grounded ice basal sliding is computed using a Weertman-Budd-type sliding law (Hindmarsh and Le Meur, 2001; Kleiner and Humbert, 2014; Calov et al., 2018), such as

$$v_b = -C_b \frac{\tau_b^p}{N_b^q} \quad (1)$$

Where

$$C_b = C_b^0 e^{T_b'/\gamma} \left(1 + \left(1 - e^{-H_w/H_w^0} \right) \right) \quad (2)$$

In equation (1), v_b is the basal sliding velocity, as a function of C_b , the sliding function, τ_b the basal shear stress and N_b the basal normal stress. The two coefficients p, q are the sliding exponents. In equation (2), C_b^0 is the sliding coefficient, T_b' the basal temperature relative to the pressure melting point, γ is the sub-melt parameter, c the water-layered-enhanced basal sliding coefficient, H_w the subglacial water-layer thickness and H_w^0 the threshold water-layer thickness. The used values can be seen in Table 1.

Quantity	value
sub-melt parameter γ	1° C
threshold water-layer thickness H_w^0	5 mm
sliding exponents p, q	3, 2
water-layered-enhanced basal sliding coefficient c	9

Table 1: Constants used in the grounded subglacial sliding law

Out of all the remaining unknowns only C_b^0 is left unknown (τ_b , N_b , T_b' and H_w are computed by SICOPOLIS). This coefficient is not easily measurable, and is dependent on location. In order to find suitable values, the AIS is first divided into the 18 IMBIE regions (Rignot and Mouginot, 2016), for each of these regions (see Figure 6), a different sliding coefficient will be iteratively computed.

Figure 6: 18 drainage basins from IMBIE and Rignot and Mouginot (2016)

The calibration run starts with the output of the 100-year smoothing run, left to run at first without any basal sliding, which is progressively turned on for the first 5000 years. It is first run with an initial guess for the sliding coefficient, which is $1 \text{ ma}^{-1} \text{Pa}^{-1}$. Then the guess is iteratively improved over the last 10 ka of the run, using an adapted algorithm by Greve et al. (2020):

For the k -th iteration of the run, we do for each of the drainage basins n a linear regression through the origin, of the observed (Rignot et al., 2017) and simulated surface velocities, hence:

$$(v_{sim})_n^k = a_n^k \cdot (v_{obs})_n^k \quad (3)$$

Where we want to have the slope a_n for each region to go as close as possible to 1. In order to minimize it, first we pass the former linear regression through \log (v_{sim} and v_{obs} are positive quantities, and are subject to a strictly positive minimum value, and \log is base 10), which gives:

$$y_i = x_i + b \quad (4)$$

Where the n and k indexes are dropped for readability, and

$$\begin{aligned} y_i &= \log(v_{sim})_n^k \\ x_i &= \log(v_{obs})_n^k \\ b &= \log a_n^k \end{aligned}$$

Equation (4) is computed using the least squares methods, such as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^I (y_i - (x_i + b))^2 \rightarrow \min \quad (5)$$

With $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, I\}$ denoting the grid point number in a single drainage region. We can then differentiate Equation (5) with respect to b , which we want to equate to 0 because of the minima condition. Note that b is independent of the grid point. Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial b} \left(\sum_{i=1}^I (y_i - (x_i + b))^2 \right) &= \sum_{i=1}^I \frac{\partial}{\partial b} (y_i - (x_i + b))^2 = 0 \\ &\Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^I -2 \cdot (y_i - (x_i + b)) = 0 \\ &\Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^I (y_i - x_i) - \sum_{i=1}^I b = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Since b is independent of the grid point, we get that $\sum_{i=1}^I b = I \cdot b$. Which finally gives us:

$$\begin{aligned} b &= \frac{1}{I} \sum_{i=1}^I (y_i - x_i) \\ \Rightarrow \log(a_n^k) &= \frac{1}{I} \sum_{i=1}^I \log \frac{(v_{sim})_n^k}{(v_{obs})_n^k} \end{aligned}$$

This tells us that the logarithm of the slope is the arithmetic mean of the logarithmic ratio of the simulated to observed surface velocities. We can finally get the slope value a_n^k :

$$a_n^k = 10^b \quad (6)$$

Which we can use to update the basal sliding coefficient of the following iteration. This allows us to formulate a recursive definition of the sliding coefficient $((C_b^0)_n^k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$:

$$\begin{aligned} k = 0 : (C_b^0)_n^0 &= 1 \text{ m a}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1} \\ \forall k \in \mathbb{N}^* : (C_b^0)_n^k &= \frac{(C_b^0)_n^{k-1}}{a_n^{k-1}} \end{aligned}$$

However, the updating of the sliding coefficients seemed to be too aggressive, and some periodic evolutions of the sliding coefficients developed in some regions, around the value of 1, not showing any signs of convergence. Thus, starting from the 3rd iteration, the sliding coefficient is updated as follows:

$$\forall k \geq 3 : (C_b^0)_n^k = \frac{(C_b^0)_n^{k-1}}{a_n^{k-1} \cdot \alpha + (1 - \alpha)}$$

Where α is a modifier, here $\alpha = 0.5$, allowing the sliding coefficient to update less aggressively and stay on one either the upper or lower bounds of 1, thus removing any periodic behaviors. The function $f(\alpha) = a_n^{k-1} \cdot \alpha + (1 - \alpha)$ with $\alpha \in [0; 1]$ is a linear interpolation function between a_n^{k-1} and 1.

It is important to note that this sliding coefficient calibration is only done by looking at the surface velocities of grounded ice, and does not take into account the ice shelves.

Having this, the next step for the protocol was the implementation. In order to streamline this algorithm that will be used on three different runs, and one more time during the Holocene phase, we decided to automate it using `python3`. This program takes as an input the output from the initial run with $(C_b^0)_n^0 = 1 \text{ m a}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$, computes the next iteration's sliding coefficient before creating a new run, using the

correct parameters, and then running it. It then waits until the end of this run, and starts again. The stopping conditions are either a specific value wanted for the overall slope over the AIS, or simply after a certain number of iterations.

4.2.2 Glacial phase

The idea behind this phase is to emulate the last glacial maximum, when the AIS was larger and thicker than today's. This way, the ice sheet will retain this 'memory' of this past time. For this purpose, no nudging is employed, the ice sheet is left to freely evolve. However, during testing, most of Antarctica would gain mass except around Thwaites glacier region. Previously, the ice shelf basal melting followed a sector-wise parametrization by Greve and Galton-Fenzi (2017), but in order to allow the AIS to gain more mass, the ice shelf basal melting was turned off for this phase.

The only other forcing employed in this phase are the surface temperature anomaly and the sea level records, as we can see in Figure 7. The simulation takes as an input the output from the calibration phase, and using the same sliding coefficients. It lasts for around 100 ka before the end of this phase.

4.2.3 Deglacial phase

The deglacial phase constitutes the initial stage of the shorter simulation runs, commencing at -20 ka and spanning a duration of 11 ka. Its primary objective is to serve as a transitional period between the glacial phase and the present-day conditions. Extensive testing was conducted during this phase, as it was crucial to ensure that mass loss from the Antarctic Ice Sheet (AIS) occurred while preserving the overall geometry. The focus of these tests primarily revolved around the parameters associated with the nudging technique since allowing for free evolution did not facilitate mass loss. However, a majority of the simulations resulted in significant or complete loss of the Pine-Island/Thwaites glacier region. To address these issues, the nudging technique, as described earlier, was employed, with progressively tighter geometry

Figure 7: Surface temperature anomaly by Petit et al. (1999) (top) and sea level anomaly by Imbrie et al. (1984) (bottom) between the start of the glacial phase and today.

constraints over time.

Furthermore, this phase also involved testing at a resolution of 32 km. However, the initial simulations at a resolution of 16 km were initiated during this stage. These simulations utilized the output from the glacial phase as input, with the resolution doubled through the utilization of the `resolution_doubler` tool native to SICOPOLIS.

4.2.4 Holocene phase

The primary objective of this final phase is to bring the AIS to an accurate present-day geometry, along with matching surface velocity fields. This is accomplished through a combination of nudging for geometry adjustment and another round of iterative sliding coefficient refinement.

In this phase, the basal melting of the ice shelves is reintroduced, utilizing a sector-wise parametrization method (Greve and Galton-Fenzi, 2017). During the first 5.5 ka of the Holocene period, a strategy similar to the deglacial phase is employed until reaching the time point of -4.5 ka.

Subsequently, a sliding coefficient adjustment process similar to the one conducted during the Calibration phase is repeated, this time at a higher resolution of 16 km. Due to the increased computational time required, only 500 years of relaxation after the coefficient adjustment are utilized. In this phase, only five iterations are performed, as fifteen iterations were already carried out during the calibration phase. The same algorithm described in the calibration phase section is employed, using the final sliding coefficients obtained from the calibration phase as the initial values.

For the last 4000 years, leading up to the present-day, a newer ice-shelf basal melting parametrization method, as used in the ISMIP-6 Antarctica experiment (Seroussi et al., 2020), is employed. This choice facilitates a seamless transition to future climate simulations of the ISMIP-6 type.

4.3 Ice sheet memory

In order to evaluate the presence of the thermal and GIA signals, a steady-state spin-up, very similar to the calibration phase, with the sliding coefficient inversion:

- identical to the calibration run, 100 ka at 32 km, with the same sliding coefficient tuning.

- 7000 years at 16 km resolution using the resolution doubler on the output of the 100 ka run
- Another round of sliding coefficient tuning at 16 km, using 500 years for relaxation
- 4000 years simulation using the newly adjusted coefficients, for a total run of 111.5 ka.

The idea behind this steady state run is to have similar calibration to the framework tested in this thesis, with a constrained geometry for an extended period of time in order to develop the 3-D temperature field, which was not present in the snapshots of Antarctica given to the model at initialization. Then, comparisons can be drawn between the result of this steady-state spin-up, and our new protocol, by comparing basal temperature fields and upward bed velocities.

4.4 Future control run

The final section of this study focuses on testing the framework through a future control run, simulating a steady-state present climate scenario. This climate state is derived by averaging the surface temperature and the surface mass balance (SMB) over the last 30 years of the Holocene phase, including the SMB correction due to the topography nudging. These averaged values are then utilized as input for the future climate run. The purpose of this future climate run is to allow the ice sheet to evolve autonomously, without any geometry constraints or nudging, over a period of 300 years.

By conducting this future climate run, we aim to examine the ice sheet's behavior under different initial conditions, without the influence of geometry constraints or nudging techniques. Additionally, a comparative analysis can be performed by conducting a steady-state run using the previously mentioned steady-state spin-up method.

This comparison will enable us to evaluate the impact of different initial conditions on the evolution of the ice sheet.

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Transient spin-up framework

5.1.1 Calibration phase

At first, the calibration scheme was left to run with a very strict stopping condition: every region's slope should be around unity within 5% of error. However, after more than 30 iterations, it was clear that these conditions were too strict. In fact, as we can see in Figure 8, the sliding coefficients would stop evolving in a meaningful manner after a few iterations. Thus, iterations were restricted to 15 in order to save on computational time.

Figure 8: Evolution of the sliding coefficient over iteration, for Aq1 GHF.

The colors represent each drainage basins.

The results of this iterative process can be seen in Figure 9. As we can see, higher values of sliding coefficients are found in the Purucker GHF (especially in the East Marie Byrd land), has an overall lower GHF, resulting in overall lower sliding velocity. The higher value for the sliding coefficient allows for better matching of the surface

velocities. Martos and Aq1 are closer together in every region.

We can also see the slope of the linear regression between the simulated and observed surface velocities for every region as well as the weighted average for the entirety of the Antarctica continental region in Figure 10, we get a final slope of around 1.20 for each simulation.

Figure 9: Sliding coefficients, in $1 \text{ m a}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ for each drainage basin regions, top-left: Purucker GHF. Top-right: Martos GHF. Bottom: Aq1 GHF.

Figure 10: Evolution of the slope in the linear regression described earlier, for each region in respect with iteration. The thicker line is the weighted average for the slope where the weights are the fractional area of each region. The dotted line is a slope of unity.

5.1.2 Glacial phase

First we can check the mass gain in Figure 11. As we can see, the Purucker (denoted Pu), gains much more mass than the Martos and Aq1 GHF datasets because of the lower overall heat flux in the Purucker GHF. Martos and Aq1 gain around 5 m of ice volume in sea level equivalent. The overall regional gain of mass gain be seen in more details in Figure 12. Again, we can see much more mass gains for the Purucker, especially in the East Antarctic Ice Sheet, again due to the lower GHF in this dataset. The difference in GHF in the EAIS is visible in Figure 4.

However, we can see that in all cases, quite a lot of mass is lost around Thwaites glacier. We do not have a complete collapse of the region at the very least. This instability is a recurring problem in the tests for the following phases, as this region collapses very easily. We can also see that quite a bit of mass is lost around the grounding lines, which may be caused by the low resolution. Since there is no sub-

Figure 11: AIS ice volume in sea level equivalent through the glacial phase, for the three different GHFs.

grid handling for the grounding lines, the grid square is either entirely grounded or floating, which in turn accelerates the ice. There may also be some loss of buttressing glacier due to the strict calving rule in SICOPOLIS (see Section 2).

5.1.3 Deglacial phase

This phase is the first one using the doubled resolution. A lot of testing went into this phase, as the melting needs to be smooth enough (no sharp loss of mass), and in a way that resembles the present-day ice sheet. For example, many tests ended with the disappearance of region around Thwaites glacier. Some of those tests can be seen in Figure 13 and 14. The 23rd test was picked to continue the spin-up protocol, with the nudging starting as soon as the simulation starts, and linearly increasing in strength until 4000 years after the end of the run. The relaxation time is 3000 years, allowing a smooth transition. The results for each of the GHFs are very similar because of the nudging technique. The overall ice volume evolution can be seen in Figure 15. More mass is lost from the Purucker GHF because of the overall higher mass gained by this

Figure 12: Ice thickness difference between the simulated last glacial maximum AIS and the observed AIS (BedMachine3). Top-left: Purucker GHF. Top-right: Martos GHF. Bottom: Aq1 GHF. Colorbar in m

specific run during the glacial phase. All runs meet closely towards the end of the phase, as the nudging constraints are tightening towards the end of the simulation. The goal of this phase was to get an approximately accurate present-day ice sheet as a transition to the Holocene phase. As we can see in Figure 14 (Right-side), the final ice sheet retains its shape. Mass is gained in the Antarctic Peninsula, and in a few places around the coastal margins of Antarctica. Some mass is lost around the Thwaites glacier, but on a smaller scale and amplitude than the mass loss seen in the rejected test runs.

Figure 13: Top-row: ice volume in sea level equivalent over time, throughout the deglacial phase. Each column describes the same run. Bottom-row: Ice thickness difference between the simulated and the observed present-day ice sheet at the end of the deglacial phase. Left: No nudging is employed, and the Thwaites region collapses, although the ice sheet is not losing much mass over the run. Right: Here the nudging is too strong, and the ice sheet loses most of the gained mass within a few hundred years. The final ice sheet is very similar.

Figure 14: Top-row: Ice volume in sea level equivalent over time, throughout the deglacial phase. Each column describes the same run. Bottom-row: Ice thickness difference between the simulated ice sheet and BedMachine3 at the end of the deglacial phase. Left: Nudging too strong too fast, the ice volume is decreasing in a more physical way, but we still see major mass loss in the Thwaites region. Right: The chosen run, with physical mass gain, and minimal mass loss in the problematic Thwaites region.

Figure 15: Ice volume in sea level equivalent for the three GHFs over the deglacial phase.

5.1.4 Holocene phase

This phase has two purposes: Fine-tuning the ice geometry, and doing another round of sliding coefficient calibration, at the resolution of 16 km. This is separated in 3 different sub-phases.

The testing for the timing of those sub-phases was done at 32 km, for which the ice volume evolution can be seen in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Ice volume in sea level equivalent for Aq1 GHF, the volume continues to decrease until around -4500 years. This is the moment we chose to start the second calibration phase because of the pseudo-equilibrium attained around that time. The relaxation times for the iterated values of sliding coefficients being 500 years, this leaves 4000 years of relaxation for the freshly computed sliding coefficients. The dotted line is the ice volume of the very first smoothing run described in Section 4.1.1

5.1.4.1 Fine-tuning of parameters

This phase consists of 5 iterations of the sliding coefficient adjustment scheme described in the methods section. Since the first round of calibration was done at 32 km resolution, another round of calibration was done at 16 km of resolution. This also allows the calibration to happen after the melting of the LGM-sized ice sheet.

Immediately, we can see a great improvement in the weighted average slope of the linear regression done on the observed and simulated surface velocities, going from

Figure 17: Evolution of slope in the linear regression between observed and simulated surface velocities for the Aq1 GHF.

around 1.20 at the end of the first calibration to a slope of 1.07 to 1.03 before the second calibration run (at 16 km resolution), much closer to unity. The sources of this major improvement before any calibration may come from the more accurate 3-D temperature distribution due to the past existence of the larger ice sheet. This may also be explained by the higher resolution, which allows for a more accurate bed topography and thus computation of velocity fields. An example of the slope improvement can be seen in Figure 17. The strongest improvement seems to come from the tip of the Antarctic Peninsula (labelled 14 in Figure 6), but it does not contribute as much as the other regions to the weighted average slope as its surface area is one of the smallest.

The slopes went from 1.03 to 1.02 for the Purucker GHF, from 1.08 to 1.06 for Martos and from 1.05 to 1.02 for the Aq1 GHF.

Figure 18: Sliding coefficients, in $\text{ma}^{-1}\text{Pa}^{-1}$ for each drainage basin regions in at the end of the Holocene phase. Top-left: Purucker GHF. Top-right: Martos GHF. Bottom: Aq1 GHF.

The final sliding coefficients used for the rest of the spin-up and the control run can be seen in Figure 18. Compared to the previously obtained coefficients seen in Figure 9. We notice that across all GHF datasets, the East Mary Bird land's (c.f. region 9 in Figure 6) coefficients increase significantly, especially for the Purucker GHF, probably due to the lower GHF in the region compared to the other datasets.

Figure 19: Evolution of sliding coefficient against iteration for the Aq1 GHF.

Figure 20: Ice volume in sea-level equivalent for the Aq1 GHF throughout the Holocene phase over time

We can also see that the sliding coefficient of the largest drainage basin in the EAIS (Region 17 in Figure 6). The previously mentioned tip of the Antarctic Peninsula (Region 14 in Figure 6) also had its coefficients decreased significantly. The rest of the drainage basins seemed to have been through less variation than those three regions, which can be seen in Figure 19 (Only Aq1 GHF, for reference). The overall ice volume evolution can be seen in Figure 20.

5.2 The present day ice sheet

The last part of the Holocene phase is a continuation towards present-day geometry, with the constraints being tighter, using the previously obtained sliding coefficients. In this section we will analyze the ice sheet obtained at the end of the Holocene phase.

5.2.1 Topography

First, we will analyze the general topography of the simulated AIS: the lithosphere and ice thickness. We can study those by comparing the simulated results to the BedMachine3 topography.

The simulated ice thickness closely matches the observed ice thickness, as we can see in Figure 21. The root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) from the observed ice thickness is 88 m for the Aq1 and Purucker GHF, and 91 m for Martos. However, as we can see in Figure 21, two outlier areas are present, around Shackleton range (next to the Filchner ice shelf) and in the Amery ice shelf, respectively. Due to a lack of time, the source of those two outliers could not be tracked. Both of them seem to come from an edge case scenario in SICOPOLIS, as they are considered ice-free land inside an inland ice shelf and ocean inside an ice shelf, respectively. The bulk of the deviation from the observed ice sheet seems to come from the edges of the AIS, where the effects of low resolution are the strongest.

Figure 21: Ice thickness difference (Simulated - BedMachine3) at the end of the Holocene phase for the Aq1 GHF. Color bar in m

Figure 22: Lithosphere elevation difference (Simulated - BedMachine3) at the end of the Holocene phase for the Aq1 GHF. Color bar in m, logarithmic scale

The simulated lithosphere topography also matches very closely with the observed bed elevation. The comparison can be seen in Figure 22. The outliers are harder to notice on this simple comparison map, but the lithosphere around Shackleton range and the Amery ice shelf seems to have risen due to the absence of ice in the area. The lithosphere elevation RMSD is of around 4.0 m in all GHFs.

5.2.2 Surface velocities

It is interesting to study the surface velocities of the simulated ice sheet, especially compared to the observed surface velocity maps by Rignot et al. (2017), and we see an overall RMSD of around 207 m a^{-1} for all GHFs. This can be seen in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Surface velocity difference (Simulated - Measured Rignot et al. (2017)) at the end of the Holocene phase for the Aq1 GHF. Logarithmic color bar, in m/a.

Figure 24: Surface velocity maps, in m a^{-1} . Top-left: Observed surface velocity by Rignot et al. (2017). Top-right: Simulated surface velocity (Aq1 GHF). Bottom : Simulated surface velocity (Purucker GHF)

The initial RMSD value mentioned above encompasses the ice shelves, which are not accounted for in the tuning scheme for the sliding coefficients. It is noteworthy that the ice shelves, as a whole, exhibit velocities that are generally higher than the observed velocities. In the SICOPOLIS model, the ice densities within the ice shelves are assumed to be 910 kg m^{-3} throughout, disregarding the presence of lower-density firn in a considerable portion of the ice shelves in reality. The higher density assumed in the model increases the driving stress, leading to accelerated movement of the ice shelves. When excluding the ice shelves from the analysis, the RMSD reduces to approximately 185 m a^{-1} .

For a more detailed examination of the finer aspects, absolute velocity maps of the observed velocities and surface velocities can be compared side by side, as illustrated in Figure 24. It becomes apparent that numerous ice streams along the Siple Coast, are not adequately resolved in the simulation.

In a broader context, while the simulated ice sheet fails to fully resolve the finer ice streams, the overall surface velocity field closely matches the observed data across the majority of the ice sheet. Additionally, it is evident that the lower GHF values in the Purucker, particularly in the EAIS, contribute to overall lower surface velocities in the simulation.

5.3 Ice sheet memory

One of the appeals of this new spin-up protocol is the ‘memory’ from the LGM. In order to evaluate this memory, another spin-up was run for over 110 ka, employing a steady-state forcing for present-day conditions. The Aq1 GHF is used in this spin-up.

5.3.1 Glacial isostatic adjustment memory

The first component is the bed’s ‘memory’ of the past’s larger ice sheet that appeared during the glacial phase, which was not present in the steady-state spin-up that has been run in parallel.

The average uplift rate on the entire ice sheet and ice shelves of $2.8 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m a}^{-1}$ for the transient run, and $-1.3 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m a}^{-1}$, which suggests that the lithosphere is still rising due to the disappearance of the larger ice sheet present during the LGM. This is even more visible if the ice shelves are removed from this average, giving us an average velocity of $1.9 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m a}^{-1}$, one order of magnitude faster than with the ice shelves.

However, we can also see in Figure 25 the distribution of the GIA signals, which is negligibly small in the steady-state run except in the Shackleton range region and Amery ice shelves, which coincide with the outliers. On the other hand, in the transient run, we can see significantly more bed activity everywhere.

The root-mean-square deviation of the rate of change in bed topography between the two different spin-up methods is of $5.8 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m a}^{-1}$, which is higher than the average rate of changes, because of this higher bed activity on most of Antarctica compared to the steady-state spin-up, which comes to show how the ice sheet reacts to changing ice loads, and its non-negligible presence in the obtained simulated ice sheet.

Finally, we can also observe that in both runs, the Shackleton range outlier is present.

Figure 25: Rate of change of the lithosphere topography, logarithmic scale in m a^{-1} , averaged over the last 30 years of both spin-ups. Top: Steady-state spin-up. Bottom: transient spin-up.

5.3.2 Temperature memory

In order to evaluate the temperature ‘memory’ of the ice sheet, we will study the ice temperature at the bed of the ice sheet. Moreover, since the steady-state and the transient spin-ups share the same geothermal heat flux, and the bed is less affected by surface temperatures, differences should arise because of the different pasts for the two spin-ups.

And indeed, we can immediately see that the transient run yields a significantly colder bed by very close to 1°C , as the steady-state spin-up has an average bed temperature of -6.56°C compared to -7.54°C in the transient run (for grounded ice only, as the ice shelves’ bed temperature is 0°C .), with an overall root-mean-square deviation of 2.42°C .

Figure 26: Bed temperature difference between the transient and steady-state runs (transient run - steady-state, in $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The blue parts show the regions where the transient run is colder than the steady-state run. Logarithmic scale.

As we can see in Figure 26, most of the colder regions are in the WAIS, which

coincides with the parts of the ice sheet that were thicker during the colder last glacial maximum (c.f. Figure 12).

This difference in temperature may have an effect on the velocity distribution. In Figure 27 and 28, we can see the vertical mean of horizontal velocity in Antarctica. This shows us how slower the regions with lower temperatures of the AIS in the transient run compared to the steady-state spin-up are. This is probably due to the colder ice sheet we see in the EAIS.

However, we also notice that the ice shelves are faster in the transient run compared to the steady-state spin-up. The vertical mean RMSD between the two spin-ups is of 142 m a^{-1} with the faster moving shelves, and of 125 m a^{-1} without the ice shelves.

The Shackleton range outlier is also visible in the velocity maps.

Figure 27: Vertical mean of the horizontal velocity, m a^{-1} . Left: Steady-state spin-up. Right: Transient spin-up. The bluer the slower the ice moves horizontally. Logarithmic scale.

Figure 28: Vertical mean of the horizontal velocity difference between the transient and steady-state runs (transient run - steady-state). Green/blue regions are where the transient run is slower than the steady-state spin-up. Logarithmic scale, in m/a

Lastly, it may be interesting to see if similar results can be seen in the vicinity of Dome Fuji. Much of the detail is lost due to the coarse resolution of 16 km. However, we can still see in Figure 29 that the bed temperatures are substantially colder in the transient spin-up compared to the steady-state spin-up. The simulated Dome Fuji is always under the melting point in the obtained results. However, the Dome Fuji ice core DF2 obtained between 2003 and 2006 has a bed temperature at the pressure melting point (Motoyama et al., 2021). A possible reason for the discrepancy is that the real GHF in the area could be larger than what is predicted by the Aq1 dataset used for the spin-ups.

Figure 29: Top: Bed temperature in the Dome Fuji vicinity, in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the transient spin-up. Bottom: Bed temperature difference between the transient spin-up and the steady-state spin-up in the vicinity of Dome Fuji, in $^{\circ}\text{C}$, logarithmic scale.

5.4 Future control run

In this section, we can compare the AIS after a control run, without any nudging, where the ice sheet is left to evolve freely with a present-day, steady-state climate forcing. The initial conditions of those runs are the output from either the transient or the steady-state spin-up.

We can first take a look at the overall gains or losses of ice volume in Figure 30, which shows us that the ice volume increases similarly for both control runs, although the control run with transient spin-up gains more mass during the 300-year simulation. They start with a 0.1 m of volume in sea level equivalent, compared to 0.2 m at the end of the run.

We can observe in Figure 31 that the observed mass difference appears to originate primarily from the coastal margins of Antarctica, particularly in the vicinity of the Thwaites glacier and the ice shelves adjacent to Wilkes land. Additionally, there is a noticeable mass loss in the Shackleton range, which can be attributed to an outlier in the region.

Analyzing the ice temperature, we find that the control run with the transient spin-up still exhibits colder temperatures than the control run with steady-state spin-up (see Figure 32), with an average lower bed temperature by 1°C . The RMSD is calculated to be 2.2°C . However, a distinct pattern emerges when considering the lithosphere elevation velocity. Upon closer examination, it becomes apparent that the lithosphere in the control run with the steady-state spin-up is rising significantly faster in specific regions: the Thwaites glacier, Shackleton range, Wilkes land, and Ross ice shelf. This phenomenon is visually depicted in Figure 33.

These two future control simulations, albeit brief, highlight the influence of the Antarctic Ice Sheet's historical evolution on the outcomes of identical simulations when left to evolve autonomously. Longer control runs and future climate simulations comparing the two spin-up methods would be preferable, as 300 year may be too short for significant differences to appear, especially in the control run.

Figure 30: Ice volume in sea level equivalent for the two control runs (transient and steady-state spin-ups).

Figure 31: Ice thickness difference between the control run with the transient spin-up and the control run with the steady-state spin-up, in m, logarithmic scale.

Figure 32: Bed temperature difference between the control run with transient spin-up and the control run with steady-state spin-up, in $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The blue parts show the regions where the transient run is colder than the steady-state run. Logarithmic scale.

Figure 33: Rate of change of the lithosphere topography, in m a^{-1} . Top: control run with the steady-state spin-up. Bottom: control run with the transient spin-up.

6 Conclusion

The initialization process for an ice sheet model simulation is a multifaceted undertaking that carries significant implications for the outcomes of future climate simulations. In this thesis, we have introduced a novel spin-up protocol designed to facilitate a robust reconstruction of Antarctica's historical conditions. However, it is important to note that this protocol is computationally demanding.

Our findings align with relevant reconstructions, revealing that the simulated ice sheet during the LGM is considerably larger in terms of both volume and grounded ice area compared to the present-day configuration. Notably, the present-day ice sheet retains the imprint of the LGM through englacial temperature patterns and residual isostatic uplift. Furthermore, it accurately captures the current geometry and exhibits a surface velocity field that reasonably aligns with observational data.

During the simulations, two outliers have emerged, warranting further investigation. Regrettably, due to the extended computational times associated with our spin-up protocol, we were unable to conduct a comprehensive examination of these localized regions exhibiting unphysical behavior. Nevertheless, it is important to emphasize that these outliers are confined to specific areas and have been identified since their occurrence. Thus, the proof of concept remains valid for the overall Antarctic Ice Sheet.

This memory retention, as evidenced by the persistent influence of LGM conditions, has a discernible impact on future control runs performed using present-day climate forcing. The influence of past conditions is clearly visible in the outcomes of these simulations, underscoring the significance of accurate initialization for reliable projections of future ice sheet behavior.

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